

- MINI-DISSERTATION -

**The new old Afghanistan: The legitimacy of the Taliban regime and the
consequences of denied recognition.**

by

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Summary of Dissertation:

This summary seeks to highlight the critical points of the following dissertation. It begins with the introduction to the dissertation (Chapter 1), highlighting the fall of Afghanistan to the Taliban and the group's subsequent proclamation of a new government and the denial of that government's legitimacy by the United Nations. The dissertation then asks two questions: Is the Taliban-led government in Afghanistan a legitimate government in terms of international law and what will the consequences of continued denial to recognise this Taliban government be?

The first question is asked in Chapter 2, where it is analysed in 4 parts: The requirements for forming a government under international law, the status of the "de facto" government under international law, the recognition of terrorist organisations as legitimate governments and the impact of human rights on recognition of governments. The chapter ends by concluding that the Taliban have indeed formed a legitimate government in terms of international law.

The second question is asked in Chapter 3, where it is analysed in 3 parts: The act of non-recognition by a government or state, human rights and its impact on non-recognition and the consequences of not recognising the Taliban government in Afghanistan. The chapter ends by highlighting the total exclusion of the Taliban government from global decision-making processes, as well as global financial and humanitarian institutions.

Chapter 4 concludes the dissertation. It highlights and summarises the points made and conclusions reached through Chapters 3 and 4, and notes that the Taliban will have to either adapt its political doctrines to align more closely with global standards and values, or content itself with being a rogue state, locked outside the global order for the foreseeable future.

Chapter 1: Introduction

On the 7th of September 2021, the Taliban declared a new “caretaker government” in the Afghan capital of Kabul, following their defeat of the UN-backed civilian government. This new Afghanistan, formally the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan, will be ruled by the Taliban under a strict interpretation of Islamic law, bringing into question the human rights protections of groups such as Afghan women, the Afghan LGBTQ+ community, Afghan religious minorities and Afghans still clinging to the dream of a democratic Afghanistan.

Consequently, recognition of this Taliban-led regime as the legitimate government of Afghanistan has become a problem for the international community. At the time of writing, most UN member states, including the UK, the US, and members of the EU, have not recognised the Taliban government as the legitimate government of Afghanistan. However, a few nations have begun to break ranks. The Foreign Minister of Turkey has called on nations to recognise the Taliban regime, as recognition will help formalise humanitarian aid to the war-ravaged Afghanistan.¹ The Taliban has also held meetings with foreign ministers from Bahrain, Finland, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Lebanon, Qatar, Somalia, Venezuela, and with the US special representative for Afghanistan.²

The purpose of this dissertation is to determine the consequences of such denied recognition of the Taliban government, especially since the Taliban has shown interest in fostering international acceptance of its legitimacy. As the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan extends diplomatic feelers out into the wider world, it would be prudent to establish a legal rather than a political framework to determine its governmental legitimacy.

Thus, the first question must be asked: Can the Taliban, terrorist organisation and international pariah, establish a government that complies with international legal criteria?

To answer this question, I will first look at three key issues pertaining to governments, and the Taliban itself, that are regulated by international law. The first is the requirements posed by international law of an institution to be recognized as a government, and the application thereof to the Taliban in Afghanistan. The second is the definition of the Taliban regime as a “de facto”

¹ <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/10/14/taliban-delegation-in-ankara-for-talks-with-turkish-officials>

[Accessed 3 October 2022]

² *ibid*

regime and that definition's legal consequences. The third is the establishment of a government by a group that, in terms of international consensus and international law, has been branded a terrorist organisation and has been identified as a regime that shows little regard for international human rights.

The second question posed in this dissertation will focus on the effects of the continuing refusal by the international community to recognise the Taliban government. This question will also be divided into smaller inquiries. The first will be a discussion on the act of recognition itself in international law and the role the law plays in the legitimising, or delegitimising, of a new government. The second is an exploration of the consequences, both immediate and long-term, of a continued refusal of recognition of a nation's role on the international stage, and the impact it will have on the government and the people of Afghanistan specifically.

Chapter 2: The legitimacy of the Taliban regime under international law

The first and most pertinent question surrounding the Taliban government is quite simple: Is it a legitimate government in terms of international law? To answer this, the international legal criteria for statehood and recognition of statehood must be discussed and understood before the Taliban government can be measured against such criteria.

2.1 The requirements for an effective government:

When determining the validity of an entity's claim to statehood, the existence of a government is a primary requirement to be met by the prospective 'state'. In the case of Afghanistan, the state already exists, and the state purports to have a government. The key question is therefore if its governing authority is legitimate.

When defining a government in terms of international law, the South African case of *S v Banda*³ identified that for a state to have a government, that government must be in control of its own territory and must be independent of any other authority.⁴ In addition, Oppenheim states that where a government "is in fact in control of the country and which enjoys the habitual obedience of the bulk of the population with the reasonable expectancy of permanence, can be said to represent the state in question...".⁵ Indeed, Crawford notes that the establishment of a

³*S v Banda* 1989 (4) SA 519 (B)

⁴ *ibid* 540E-F

⁵ Robert Jennings and Arthur Watts (eds) *Oppenheim's International Law* 9 ed (1992) vol. 1, 150

government may be the single most important requirement for statehood, as all other requirements for statehood hinge on a government's ability to conduct itself effectively.⁶ It is after all a government that controls the territory that comprises a state, governs the people within the state and engages in foreign affairs in the interest of the state. Without a government, no central authority exists to claim the right to statehood, and a state can thus not exist.

But what is an "effective government"? Crawford identifies it as follows: 1. The actual exercise of authority; 2. The right or title to exercise the authority.⁷ To illustrate his point, he cites the independence of the Democratic Republic of Congo from Belgium in 1960. Prior to 1960, Belgium had both these governmental rights regarding the territory, people, and foreign affairs of the Congo. By withdrawing from its role as controller of the government and ceding these rights to local Congolese authorities, the Republic of the Congo could come into being as a sovereign nation.⁸ Therefore an effective government, one that has the capability to meet the other classical criteria for statehood, must have the actual ability to govern and some right or title right to govern as the sole effective government.

Based on the above, I would argue that there are at least four key criteria to be met by a government in order to be seen as an "effective government" in terms of international law. These criteria are: 1. The body must be in control of all the territory that makes up the state. 2. The body must enjoy the habitual obedience of the bulk of the population of the state. 3. The body must expect to continue its existence with some reasonable degree of permanence. 4. The body must be independent of the control of an outside authority. These four criteria will now be used to determine if the Taliban regime can be considered the legitimate new government of Afghanistan.

2.1.1 Control of all the territory that comprises the state

One of the first ways of determining a government's efficacy is determining how well it controls the territory of the state it governs. If the government of the state does not have the capacity to govern the territory of the state, the state has no means of controlling its population or conducting itself in the international arena. Determining if the government is in fact in control of all its territory is therefore a pertinent and crucial issue.

⁶ James Crawford *The Creation of States in International Law* 2 ed (2006) 56

⁷ *ibid* 57

⁸ *ibid*

While the assumption that all governments control their state's territory totally is an admirable and ideal one, it only takes casual contemporary observation to recognise that not all states can abide by this principle. Multiple Sub-Saharan and Middle Eastern governments have struggled for decades to retain effective control over the territory that comprises their states.⁹ These struggles are due to a multiplicity of factors, including rebel militias, weak governmental institutions, systemic corruption and underdeveloped economies and industrial capabilities.

Does this then mean that a lack of total control leads to a government being seen as illegitimate and not representing the state in international affairs? This narrow view leads to problems. To illustrate, I will again make an example of the Belgian Congo, now the Democratic Republic of the Congo. The DRC is infamous for its fragmented political nature, with multiple militia groups claiming vast swathes of Congolese territory.¹⁰ The government in Kinshasa, in turn, is in no position to root out effectively these militia groups and claim to be in total control of the territory of the DRC. If the above-mentioned principle of total control over the territory of the state were to be applied narrowly, this would mean that the DRC, or any other government not in full control of the territory of the state, would result in the government being unable to be classified as the effective government of the state under international law. And yet, the government in Kinshasa is still recognised as the effective government of the DRC, receiving, and sending diplomats to and from other states and being represented in the United Nations General Assembly by diplomats it appointed. It is obvious then that lack of control over some or even most of a state by its government does not delegitimize a government.

Afghanistan did, and arguably still does, form part of the group of nations whose governments cannot claim to control the entirety of their state's territory. Even prior to American intervention in Afghan affairs in the early 2000's, Afghanistan as a modern state is a more ambiguous concept than many realise. Kissinger notes that: "[t]raditionally, Afghanistan has been less a state in the conventional sense, than a geographic expression for an area never brought under the consistent administration of any single authority. For most of recorded history, Afghan tribes and sects have been at war with each other, briefly uniting to resist invasion or to launch marauding raids against their neighbours. Elites in Kabul might undertake periodic experiments with parliamentary institutions, but outside the capital, an ancient tribal

⁹ See Jason Stearns *Dancing in the Glory of Monsters: The Collapse of the Congo and the Great War of Africa* (2012) 122-209; Cherif Bassiouni *Libya: From Repression to Revolution: A Record of Armed Conflict and International Law Violations, 2011-2013* (2013) 158-184; Nikolaos van Dam *Destroying a Nation: The Civil War in Syria* (2017) 64-77

¹⁰ Jason Stearns (n 9) 122-209

code of honour predominated.”¹¹ This state of being is why Afghanistan proved incredibly difficult to bring into historical and contemporary world orders, first by the British, then the Russian Empire, the Soviet Union and finally the United States. It exists not as a unitary state like South Africa or even a federation like Russia or the United States, but more as Germany was prior to its unification in the 19th century: a distinct geographical region where peoples of similar historical, cultural, and linguistic ties live, but with very distinct and disparate political and tribal polities existing within the region.

How does this political and diplomatic reality of Afghanistan then relate to the legal requirement for the government to control the territory of the state? In short, minimally at best. While the tribal nature of Afghanistan’s population does mean that the Taliban regime exercises only partial influence over the people who live beyond Kabul itself, they are still recognised as the controllers of the state of Afghanistan itself, if not the absolute controller of every corner of the territory it comprises. Kissinger too recognises that the tribal polities of Afghanistan are only “semi-autonomous”¹², meaning that there is still general recognition by the populace that they live in Afghanistan, and that they are governed by a central authority. A good example of this general recognition can be seen in the Afghan tribal practice of a *loya jirga* (great council), where prominent tribal elders gather to elect new heads of state, assent to a new constitution or resolve key governmental issues. These council meetings have in contemporary times been held in Kabul, with the participation of the central Afghan government, indicating that the tribes of Afghanistan do indeed recognise Kabul as the central authority of the state of Afghanistan, if not also that Kabul recognises the need to include the tribes in the Afghan hinterland in its decision-making. A *loya jirga* was in fact held both to recognise the American-backed Republican government in 2001, and again to recognise the Taliban regime in 2022.¹³ Thus, the first requirement needed for an effective government is met by the Taliban regime.

2.1.2 The habitual obedience of the bulk of the population of the state

To determine if a government enjoys the habitual obedience of the bulk of the population of the state, a practical observation, rather than a moral investigation, is required. The word “obedience” in the definition indicates that the legal mandate to govern is afforded not based

¹¹ Henry Kissinger *World Order* (2014)

¹² *ibid*

¹³ ‘Taliban convene 'Loya Jirga' in Kabul’ *Times of India* 28 June 2022

on principles of democracy or the consent of the governed, but the mere obeying of the government, irrespective of its character.¹⁴ The word “bulk” however, does indicate that majority obedience is not an absolute prerequisite for a government to be seen as an effective government in international law.¹⁵ The definition is also noticeably devoid of any notions of democratic legitimacy. Popular support or the people’s mandate is not required for a government to be considered the effective government of a state, merely that a large enough portion of the population recognises the government as the sole authority in the state.

A contemporary example is the government of totalitarian Belarus. Even during the mass protests and popular disapproval of the Lukashenko regime in 2020 and 2021, the regime is still considered the effective government of Belarus by the UN and the members of the UNSC.¹⁶ Another is Saudi Arabia, one of the few nations in the UN that does not identify itself as a democracy, instead identifying as an absolute monarchy.¹⁷ While it is certainly not democratic, the people of Saudi Arabia still recognise this form of government as the sole authority in Saudi Arabia, thus meeting this specific requirement for effective government.¹⁸

In the current Afghan context, the Taliban has no major political opposition in the form of other political parties or rebellious provinces. It is also ensuring the obedience of its populace by cracking down on dissent through censorship and political violence.¹⁹ While these acts are morally reprehensible, they do not factor into the legal prerequisites for an effective government. As also mentioned above when discussing the first requirement for effective government, the Afghan *loya jirga* assembled and legitimised the Taliban as the sole authority of Afghanistan²⁰. While not a democratic process, such expression of regional support is sufficient to legitimize other totalitarian regimes. Thus, the Taliban regime also satisfies this requirement.

2.1.3 The expectation to continue its existence with some reasonable degree of permanence
For any government to be considered an effective government, it needs to exist long enough to exercise its control over the state and the people living in it. The question to be answered here

¹⁴ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/obedience> [Accessed 24 October 2022]

¹⁵ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/bulk> [Accessed 24 October 2022]

¹⁶ <https://un.mfa.gov.by/en/404/> [Accessed 24 October 2022]

¹⁷ <https://www.britannica.com/place/Saudi-Arabia> [Accessed 24 October 2022]

¹⁸ *ibid*

¹⁹ United Nations Assistance Mission in Afghanistan “Human Rights in Afghanistan” (2021)

²⁰ ‘Taliban convene 'Loya Jirga' in Kabul’ (n 13)

is then what constitutes a “reasonable degree of permanence” where government control is concerned.

Under a constitutional process, changes of government are structured and predictable events, usually in the form of elections or rules of succession. It also gives the outside observer the chance to determine how long the current government will be in control of the state. A determinable term of office in democracies, indefinite rule in autocracies.²¹ If changes of government happen outside the constitutional order, this structure and predictability are removed, and determining how long a regime will stay in power becomes a day-by-day analysis. Dugard notes that states, when confronted with governmental change outside the constitutional order, withhold their recognition until they can be certain that the regime is here to stay.²² This indicates that states want to be sure that the new regime is a permanent fixture on the international stage, that will speak to its own or its state’s interest for the foreseeable future.

The degree of permanence of the regime’s hold on power is also influenced by the number of competitors the regime may have, and the intensity of that competition. If there are multiple claimants to the title of legitimate governing authority of a state, third party states are likely to withhold any recognition until a group emerges that is strong enough and stable enough to be considered the sole governing authority.²³ Indeed, this policy is reflected in the position taken by the UK in 1980, where they indicated that they “...shall continue to decide the nature of our dealings with regimes which come to power unconstitutionally in the light of our assessment of whether they are able of themselves to exercise effective control of the territory of the state concerned and seem likely to continue to do so”.²⁴

With regards to the Taliban, it is evident that the Taliban believe that they are here to stay. By the end of September 2021, they had defeated the pro-government forces of the former Afghan government.²⁵ They have had no real opponents to their claim as governing authority over Afghanistan. While a new branch of ISIL has emerged in Afghan territory, these cells have been too isolated to pose any real threat to Taliban control of the state.²⁶ In the meantime, the

²¹ Yoram Dinstein *Non-International Armed Conflict* (2014) 97

²² John Dugard “States (Including Recognition and Non-recognition)” in John Dugard and others (eds), *Dugard’s International Law: A South African Perspective* (JUTA 2018) 166

²³ Yoram Dinstein (n 17) 97

²⁴ *Hansard* HL vol. 408 cols 1121-1122

²⁵ ‘Inside the Fall of Kabul: An On-The-Ground Account’ *The New York Times* 27 August 2022

²⁶ ‘Islamic State violence dents Taliban claims of safer Afghanistan’ *Reuters* 9 November 2021

Taliban have established control fully by way of its caretaker government. The Taliban is the only true holder of governmental authority in Afghanistan, meaning it has met the requirement of continuing to control Afghanistan with some degree of permanence.

2.1.4 Being independent of the control of an outside authority

For any government to be truly effective, it cannot be under the control of an outside authority. It cannot be beholden to, dependent on or functioning with the permission of a third-party state or authority. The Bantustans were never recognised as real states controlled by real governing authorities for this exact reason, as they were entirely under the control of and dependent on South Africa for their continued existence.²⁷ I have also previously made the argument that the Soviet Republics beyond the Russian SFR were never truly independent states, as their governments were organised and authorised by the Communist Party in Moscow.²⁸

Looking at the Taliban and its history, we can see it as a wholly Afghan phenomenon. Created in the wake of the Soviet invasion of the country, former mujahideen commanders assumed the banner of Afghan Islamic fundamentalism to restore Islamic law in Afghanistan. The formation of the Taliban was an Afghan response to Afghan problems, and while members of the original group may have been trained by outside forces in their fight against the Soviet Union, new recruits were trained in Afghanistan with the purpose of imposing their rule over Afghanistan.

2.2 The “*de facto*” regime and international recognition

Now that it has been established that the requirements for effective government have been met by the Taliban regime, we need to determine where the regime stands in terms of international recognition. The United Nations has maintained the position that Afghanistan is a recognised UN-state controlled by an unrecognised “*de facto*” regime, this regime being the Taliban.²⁹ Thus, the term “*de facto*” must be explored in the framework of international legal recognition and we must determine how it affects a regime’s identity in international law.

Legal opinion on the *de facto* regime does bear precedence. Opinions such as those held by Dugard articulate that the term *de facto* indicates that a *de facto* government comes into being when third party states acknowledge the regime as the controller of a state, but do not wish to

²⁷ John Dugard ‘South Africa and International Law: A Historical Introduction’ in John Dugard and others (eds), *Dugard’s International Law: A South African Perspective* (JUTA 2018) 23

²⁸ Jan Kapp “In the shadow of a giant: Treaty succession in the post-Soviet republics” (2021) 13-14

²⁹ Ben Saul “Recognition” and the Taliban’s International Legal Status” (2021)

<https://icct.nl/publication/recognition-talibans-international-legal-status/> [Accessed 24 October 2022]

legitimise or approve of it through diplomatic recognition.³⁰ Oeter also states that the *de facto* regime exists in the international legal order.³¹ He argues that if something is to be defined as a *de facto* regime, there must be legal qualifications to be classified as such.³² It is important to note that here Oeter speaks of the *de facto* state, and not the *de facto* government. However, I believe that the qualifications that Oeter identifies can still be valuable in determining the nature of the *de facto* regime.

Oeter sets out those qualifications as follows: 1. A *de facto* regime must have some type of legal personality, meaning that they can engage in international relations, enter into agreements with third party states and bear rights and obligations under international law.³³ If third party states consent, diplomatic relations can also be established in so far as they do not extend to full recognition³⁴ (as is the case between France and North Korea³⁵). 2. A *de facto* regime is still bound by customary international law, as it still forms part of the international community that is in turn bound by customary international law. If the rules of custom are not followed, *de facto* regimes will be bound by state responsibility just as any other state.³⁶ As the ICJ noted in the Namibia advisory opinion of 1971, it is the exercise of authority within a territory and not the legitimacy by which the authority is exercised that determines the responsibility of a regime³⁷. 3. Human rights obligations are still binding on *de facto* regimes. While they may not be High Contracting Parties to human rights treaties, *de facto* regimes will still be bound by the fundamental human rights that are applicable to all states by way of customary international law and will be binding on them in their internal operations³⁸. 4. A *de facto* regime is prohibited from engaging in the use of force. A regime cannot use force against its neighbours or third-party states, just as any other state is barred from using force.³⁹ This protection is also a two-way street, as international law also prevents third party states from

³⁰ John Dugard “States (Including Recognition and Non-recognition)” (n 22) 166

³¹ Stefan Oeter “De Facto Regimes in International Law” in Władysław Czapliński & Agata Kleczkowska (eds) *Unrecognised Subjects in International Law* (2019) 68

³² *ibid*

³³ *ibid*

³⁴ *ibid*

³⁵ “Présentation de la Corée du Nord” <https://www.diplomatie.gouv.fr/fr/dossiers-pays/coree-du-nord/presentation-de-la-coree-du-nord/> [accessed 2 August 2022]

³⁶ Stefan Oeter “De Facto Regimes in International Law” (n 31) 68

³⁷ ICJ *Legal Consequences for States of the Continuous of South Africa in Namibia (South West Africa) notwithstanding Security Council Resolution 276 (1970)*, Advisory Opinion, 21 June 1971, ICJ Rep. 1971, par. 118

³⁸ Stefan Oeter “De Facto Regimes in International Law” (n 12) 69)

³⁹ *ibid* 70

using force against the *de facto* regime⁴⁰. 5. A *de facto* regime can enter into treaties with third party states.⁴¹ While there will be a line that contracting parties may not want to cross to avoid formally recognising a regime as legitimate, international law does not prevent the *de facto* regime from concluding treaties with other contracting states. Even if full treaty relations are to be avoided, less formal agreements can still be concluded by the regime and third-party states.⁴²

2.3 Recognition of a terrorist organisation as a legitimate government.

The fact of the Taliban's effective control over Afghanistan has been made evident and the legal requirements for governmental legitimacy have been met. Yet while the legal requirements have been met, a new problem asserts itself with regards to the Taliban's claim to international recognition. At the time of writing, the Taliban is still recognised as a terrorist organisation by the United Nations.⁴³ This is the single greatest barrier of entry for the Taliban into the global community of nations. It also poses a serious question: Can a terrorist organisation form a government recognised by international law as an effective government?

To determine this, an investigation into how terrorism is seen in international law, the limits placed on terrorist organisations under international law, and any analogous examples of terrorist organisations exercising governmental control over states.

2.3.1 The Taliban as a terrorist organisation:

The first declaration of the Taliban as a terrorist organisation by the UN came in Resolution 1267, adopted in 1999.⁴⁴ This resolution condemned the Taliban for harbouring al-Qaeda members, particularly Osama bin Laden⁴⁵, the use of Taliban-controlled territory as a base of terrorist operations⁴⁶ and condemning the Taliban's treatment of Afghan women and girls.⁴⁷ The resolution then calls on all nations to place economic and travel sanctions on the Taliban until there is compliance with the demands made under the resolution.⁴⁸ These resolutions were certainly not repealed when the Taliban were deposed of their leadership role in 2001, as they

⁴⁰ *ibid*

⁴¹ *ibid* 71

⁴² *ibid*

⁴³ United Nations Security Council Resolution 1267 (1999)

⁴⁴ *ibid* 1

⁴⁵ *ibid*

⁴⁶ *ibid*

⁴⁷ *ibid*

⁴⁸ *ibid* 3

continued to be identified as a terrorist organisation by the United Nations up to the present date.

2.3.2 Terrorist organisations and political legitimacy

To determine if the Taliban have legitimacy to rule over Afghanistan while being classified as a terrorist organisation, we need to look at what precedent, if any, exists where a terrorist organisation came to power in a state, constitutionally or otherwise. The example I will be looking at in this context is the Irish Republican Army (IRA) and Hamas, as both these groups aim(ed) to gain control of the governments of the states in which they primarily operated, namely Ireland and Israel/Palestine. I am purposefully excluding discussion on groups such as ISIS and others whose aims were the establishment of *new states*, not the establishment of new governments in an existing state. I also exclude groups that are deemed freedom fighters in terms of international law, such as FRELIMO and SWAPO.

I begin with the Irish Republican Army. While first formed as an armed independence movement in the early 20th century, the IRA continued its existence long after Ireland became an independent state. The main aim of the IRA was the removal of British control of Northern Ireland, thus uniting all of Ireland under Irish control.⁴⁹ It also fully rejected the authority of the British and the Irish governments, seeing itself as the only legitimate authority in Ireland.⁵⁰ The Irish government declared the IRA unlawful and the British and American governments declared the IRA a terrorist organisation.⁵¹

What became of the IRA? By 1998, as part of the Good Friday Agreement, the political wing of the IRA was allowed to form part of the Northern Irish parliament, gaining a majority in said parliament in 2022.⁵² Thus, while the IRA is still deemed a terrorist organisation in terms of international law, the custom of both the British and Irish governments reflect that a terrorist organisation can indeed achieve political legitimacy if it deradicalizes and adapts to the constitutional framework of the state it wishes to control.

The next group I will focus on is Hamas, the group in control of Palestine and *de facto* government of the Palestinian territories. The goals of Hamas are the eradication of the Israeli government and its control over the Israel/Palestine area, and the replacement of the Israeli

⁴⁹ Robert White *Out of the Ashes: An Oral History of the Provisional Irish Republican Movement* (2017) 337

⁵⁰ Richard English *Armed Struggle, the History of the IRA* (2003) 107

⁵¹ Steve Wilson et al *English Legal System* (2020) 128; Vicky Conway *Policing Twentieth Century Ireland: A History of An Garda Síochána* (2015) 101

⁵² 'Sinn Fein hails 'new era' as it wins Northern Ireland vote' *Associated Press* 7 May 2022

government with an Islamic state, like that of Iran or the Taliban's Afghanistan.⁵³ They have also been declared a terrorist organisation by the United States, the European Union, Canada, Australia, Israel, Japan, etc.⁵⁴

What is interesting about Hamas in the context of terrorism and political legitimacy, is how it came to power in Palestine. Unlike Iran and the Taliban, Hamas came to power not through unconstitutional methods like coups and civil wars, but by winning the majority of seats in the Palestinian legislative assembly.⁵⁵ As noted by Dinstein, where governments change through constitutional means, recognition of a government by a third-party state is not required.⁵⁶ What is also worth remarking, is the recognition of Palestine itself. While 138 UN member states recognise Palestine as a sovereign nation, three of the five members of the UNSC (the US, UK, and France) do not. The UN also denied a US-backed resolution to have Hamas declared as a terrorist organisation, meaning the UN does not see Hamas as a terrorist organisation. Hamas, therefore, stands as another example of a "terrorist organisation" gaining and maintaining political legitimacy through both constitutional participation in its state of operations' government and through international custom.

Thus, when we look at the Taliban as a terrorist organisation and question if that could make its political authority illegitimate, precedent reflects that where a terrorist organisation has acquired political authority in the past, it has done so through adapting to the constitutional framework of the nation within which it operates or by acquiring its political authority through constitutional methods outright. Either way, precedent and custom reflect that merely being assigned a terrorist organisation by third party states does not mean a government's authority is automatically illegitimate.

2.4 Human Rights and the Legitimacy of the Taliban Regime

Another serious obstacle to any legal discussion surrounding the Taliban's right to establish an internationally recognised government is the troubling human rights abuses that have flowed and continue to flow from the Taliban's rule of Afghanistan. The United Nations Assistance

⁵³ Pdraig O'Malley *The Two-State Delusion: Israel and Palestine – A Tale of Two Narratives* (2015) 118

⁵⁴ American Foreign Policy Council *The World Almanac of Islamism* (2014) 15; "Proscribed terrorist groups or organisations" <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/proscribed-terror-groups-or-organisations--2/proscribed-terrorist-groups-or-organisations-accessible-version> [Accessed 11 October 2022]; Matthew Levitt *Hamas: Politics, Charity, and Terrorism in the Service of Jihad* (2006) 50-51; Michael Penn *Japan and the War on Terror: Military Force and Political Pressure in the US-Japanese Alliance* (2014) 205-206

⁵⁵ Mahjoob Zweiri "The Hamas Victory: Shifting Sands or Major Earthquake?" (2006) 27 *Third World Quarterly* 675

⁵⁶ Yoram Dinstein (n 12) 98

Mission in Afghanistan (UNAMA) Human Rights Service published its report on the observation by the Taliban regime of its human rights obligations as the “*de facto* authorities” of Afghanistan.⁵⁷ In this report, UNAMA’s Human Rights Service noted multiple human rights violations. These include: indiscriminate attacks on civilians while engaging in armed conflict⁵⁸; violations of the rights to life, liberty, and physical integrity⁵⁹; violations of fundamental freedoms⁶⁰; violations of women’s rights⁶¹ and violations of judicial freedoms and prisoner’s rights.⁶² The report concludes by stating that the Taliban regime’s actions may amount to “crimes against humanity”, and that the regime must take every step possible to limit such actions and to observe and respect the human rights of all peoples within its borders.⁶³ It also calls on the international community to help those affected by these violations directly, engage with the Taliban regime on ways to improve the human rights conditions in Afghanistan and ensure that their actions do not exacerbate the conditions on the ground.⁶⁴

The failure of the Taliban to observe its human rights obligations in terms of international law is the foundational objection raised by the international community when contemplating the recognition of the Taliban regime as a legitimate government. Indeed, many nations have stated that these human rights violations mean that the regime is an “illegal government” and therefore cannot be recognised under international law. It must then be determined if the observation of human rights can indeed result in a government’s illegality under international law.

Presently, it would do well to define how human rights as a prerequisite for recognition is to be discussed in this dissertation. Its discussion is to be defined strictly around human rights as a prerequisite for recognition of the *government* of the state, not the state itself. The reason for this narrow discussion is a straightforward one; as Afghanistan is already recognised as a state by the members of the United Nations, its statehood is not in question. What is in question, is the authority of the regime that now governs it. Thus, discussing the observation of human

⁵⁷ United Nations Assistance Mission in Afghanistan “Human Rights in Afghanistan” (2021) 3

⁵⁸ *ibid*

⁵⁹ *ibid*

⁶⁰ *ibid*

⁶¹ *ibid*

⁶² *ibid*

⁶³ *ibid*

⁶⁴ *ibid*

rights as a prerequisite for the recognition of a government as opposed to a prerequisite for statehood would yield a more fruitful result.

2.4.1 The observation of human rights as a prerequisite for recognition

The argument that a government must observe and respect human rights as a prerequisite for recognition by the international community has been the subject of debate for some time. The two main lines of thought are as follows: 1. The observation of human rights should be a prerequisite for recognition, as a government that does not do so cannot be seen a legal government in the contemporary world order; 2. The observation of human rights should not be a prerequisite for recognition, as there has been no real precedent in customary international law to support it. Each of these positions deserves discussion to reach a conclusion on the Taliban regime's legitimacy.

First to be discussed is the positive argument that the observation of human rights should be a prerequisite to recognition. As noted by Dugard, how a state treats its citizens is a uniquely post-WW2 concern.⁶⁵ Concerns over human rights obligations resulted in states such as Rhodesia being denied recognition due to the racist nature of its internal governmental structure.⁶⁶ Indeed, Fawcett explains that the principle of human rights observation as a qualification of recognition was affirmed by the refusal to recognise Rhodesia's unilateral declaration of independence due to the racist structure of the Rhodesian government.⁶⁷

In the narrow interpretation of recognition of governments as opposed to states, precedent for this argument can also be found. France does not recognise the North Korean government as legitimate, specifically citing its human rights record as the reason for non-recognition.⁶⁸ Additionally, Dugard points out that: "Changes in government do not affect the personality of the state or its rights and obligations. The new government succeeds to the rights and obligations of its predecessor, however it came into existence."⁶⁹ This would mean that if a state entered into legal agreements stating that it would observe the human rights of its citizens and a successive government fails to meet or observe those obligations, it can be argued that this would result in the governments illegitimacy under international law.

⁶⁵ John Dugard "States (Including Recognition and Non-recognition)" in John Dugard and others (eds) (n 13) 134

⁶⁶ *ibid* 135

⁶⁷ James Fawcett *The Law of Nations* (1968) 38-39

⁶⁸ 'Présentation de la Corée du Nord' (n 21)

⁶⁹ John Dugard "Recognition of Governments" in John Dugard and others (eds), *Dugard's International Law: A South African Perspective* (JUTA 2018) 165

Buchanan has written prolifically on the subject of a human rights-based foundation of political legitimacy for a government in international law. In his view, what makes a regime a legitimate one is if the wielder of political power (in this case the government or regime in control of a state): 1. does a credible job of protecting at least the most basic human rights of all those over whom it wields power; and 2. provides this protection through processes, policies, and actions that themselves respect the most basic human rights.⁷⁰ He justifies this view by noting its inherent moral appeal; a wielder of such power as a government or regime can only be morally justified in exercising that power if it wields it with the intention of protecting and advancing the human rights of the people who must obey its laws.⁷¹ In fact, he argues that the moral goal of creating and seeking moral justice for the people of the state is the only justification credible enough to create a system that can so easily deny freedoms, cause harm and create and maintain inequalities.⁷²

When discussing the recognitional legitimacy of governments, Buchanan notes that while the state can be legitimate through the theory of moral theory of international law, the government can be illegitimate.⁷³ In response to the notion that refusing to recognise a regime that does not meet the requirements for recognition under the theory of moral international law, he notes that through making a clear distinction between recognising the state as a legitimate entity and the government, under the moral international legal theory the citizens of the state who are being governed by an illegitimate government or regime will be recognised within the international legal order.⁷⁴ Indeed, Buchanan points out that refusing to recognise the government and branding it illegitimate while recognising the state, the international community is able to help the citizenry oust the illegitimate regime or pressure it to reform.⁷⁵

Following the above-mentioned theories and practice and placing them in the contemporary Afghan context, present us with what I would consider the current international community's response to the Taliban regime. According to the UN, while the Taliban is an unrecognised regime ruling over the citizens of Afghanistan, the state of Afghanistan itself remains a recognised member state of the UN.⁷⁶ So, while the Taliban itself remains outside the

⁷⁰ Allen Buchanan *Justice, Legitimacy, and Self-Determination: Moral Foundations for International Law* (2004) 247

⁷¹ *ibid*

⁷² *ibid*

⁷³ *ibid* 283

⁷⁴ *ibid*

⁷⁵ *ibid*

⁷⁶ Ben Saul (n 29)

international community, the people remain a part of it. The reason the Taliban is being kept outside of the international community is also in line with the moral theory of international law. The Taliban regime, as noted in the UNAMA human rights report, does not meet the requirements set out by the moral theory. The regime's goal is not to abide by the human rights norms and frameworks established in international law, but to maintain its own order of religious, gender and democratic intolerance. Thus, by applying the moral theory of international law, the UN and the international community at large can insist that the Taliban regime is illegitimate.

Finally, it is relevant to refer to Oeter's classification of the *de facto* regime, specifically his third point that regimes are still bound by human rights law even if they exist within the traditional international legal structure. His reasoning for this is justified through the Turku Declaration of Minimum Humanitarian Standards of 1990.⁷⁷ Its essential purpose is to afford all persons, irrespective of the nations in which they live, a minimum set of human rights protections. Several articles within the declaration indicate its universal scope. Article 1 affirms that the rights afforded by the declaration apply at all times and in all instances of "public emergency".⁷⁸ Article 2 then affirms that the rights afforded in the declaration are applicable to all persons and authorities "irrespective of their legal status and without any adverse discrimination".⁷⁹ This means that, even in situations where the authorities of a given state, or even the state itself, is not recognised as legitimate, the human rights afforded in the Turku Declaration will be applicable in those areas and must be observed by the authorities in power. While protections against discrimination based on gender or race are not specifically mentioned in the Declaration, Article 3(1) indicates that "[e]veryone shall have the right to recognition everywhere as a person before the law... [t]hey shall in all circumstances be treated humanely, without any adverse distinction".⁸⁰ This article, to some extent, affirms minority, women and LGBT rights by indicating that no person may be adversely differentiated by internal laws and before internal courts.

Second to be discussed is the negative argument that the observation of human rights should not be a prerequisite for recognition. This argument is based in the fact that, while the notion of human rights observation playing a part in recognition is admirable, there is no basis for it

⁷⁷ Turku Declaration of Minimum Humanitarian Standards

⁷⁸ *ibid* Art. 1

⁷⁹ *ibid* Art. 2

⁸⁰ *ibid* Art. 3(1)

in customary international law. Dugard notes that if Fawcett's view is to be applied, many states would have their recognition revoked based on their poor human rights records.⁸¹ If Fawcett's view were only applied to new states, serious questions of fairness would have to be brought up, as it is unfair to expect higher moral standards in the conduct of new states while established states were not measured by the same standard. What would be even worse is the notion that weak states, Afghanistan in this case, are forced to conform to higher moral standards by strong states who also have chequered or downright poor human rights records.

Secondly, Dugard points out the lack of practice surrounding human rights observation as a prerequisite for recognition.⁸² Beyond France's refusal to recognise North Korea's government, very few instances comparable to it exist in contemporary state practice. A most concrete proof of the absence of human rights as a prerequisite for recognition came with the collapse of Yugoslavia. At its collapse, the European Community indicated that it would only recognise the successor states of Yugoslavia and their governments on the condition that it respected and protected human rights.⁸³ However, these successor states did not adhere to this condition. Yet, as Dugard points out, the European Community did not comply with even its own guidelines, and recognised all these states, and their offending governments, as legitimate actors on the international stage.⁸⁴ Dugard concludes by stating that recognition will always be confined to the political machinations of the United Nations, and not formal adherence to international law.⁸⁵

So, what then, is the opinion of the author of this dissertation? Firstly, I do agree with Buchanan and Oeter that human rights are fundamental parts of contemporary international law and contemporary international relations. Contemporary practice also bears out the point that most states now conduct international affairs and draft international agreements with human rights in mind. As such, it would be incredibly appealing to simply say that human rights should always form part of the recognition process.

And yet, to my mind, while it would be ideal to demand of states to observe human rights and to threaten revocation and denial of recognition when they are not observed and respected, the practicality of such a legal doctrine is disputable. It would most certainly be unevenly applied,

⁸¹ John Dugard "States (Including Recognition and Non-recognition)" (n 24) 135

⁸² *ibid*

⁸³ *ibid*

⁸⁴ *ibid* 135-136

⁸⁵ *ibid* 136

and primarily against the weaker nations of the world, while the great nations and the key allies of those nations can simply have their violations of human rights ignored or be protected by their international benefactors. In the Afghan context, I believe it would be an unfair legal principle to demand that the Taliban respect the human rights of its citizens or face illegitimacy while multiple examples of similar human rights violations have been committed by other governments and have no such threat looming over them.⁸⁶ As such, it is my opinion that human rights observation cannot be seen as a prerequisite for recognition under international law.

Chapter 3: The consequences of denied recognition

After examining what the status of the Taliban regime is under international law and determining that it is indeed a legitimate government in terms of international law, it is time to see what the international community's response to it has been and what the consequences of that reaction may be. It would be natural to assume that recognition of governments is a purely political or ideological act, but the recognition of governments by states is firmly rooted in international law and its processes are supported by custom. What then are the legal consequences of the Taliban being denied recognition by the international community?

There are a few things to discuss on this front. The first is to examine how exactly the processes of the recognition of governments by states function under international law. The second is to discuss the legal reasoning of states refusing to recognise the Taliban regime as the effective government of Afghanistan. The last point is to examine what the legal fallout of such a prolonged denial of recognition may have on the Taliban regime and the state of Afghanistan as a whole.

3.1 The act of recognition (or non-recognition) of a government by a state

As noted above, it is easy to brush off the recognition of a government by another state as a purely political or ideological exercise. While political and ideological considerations certainly play a role in determining who gets recognised at certain points in time, the act of recognition itself is in fact a legal action that is regulated by international law. Dinstein points out that:

⁸⁶ See 'Women activists, political prisoners 'sexually assaulted, tortured and executed in Saudi Arabia' jails' *Independent* 19 November 2020; <https://www.amnesty.org/en/location/asia-and-the-pacific/east-asia/china/report-china/> [Accessed 24 October 2022]; 'Torture and Abuse by Police Is the Norm in Russian Prisons' *Newsweek* 29 March 2016

“[f]oreign recognition (or non-recognition) of a government may have a far-reaching impact on its standing, rights and immunities on the internal plane – especially before the domestic courts – of the recognizing (or non-recognizing) State.”⁸⁷

It is important to note here that the recognition (or non-recognition) of a government by a state does *not* have any bearing on state creation. As ruled in the *Aguilar-Amory* case by Justice Taft, the non-recognition of a government by states cannot outweigh the evidence that a government has met the requirements for an effective government under international law.⁸⁸ Dinstein adds to this point by stating that the recognition of a government by other states cannot be seen as an additional requirement for its existence, and that the recognition of the government does not create it. The non-recognition of the government does not destroy it.⁸⁹ He cements his point by using the example of the 2001 Taliban government which was, just as the contemporary government, not recognised as the legitimate government of Afghanistan. It was not non-recognition, Dinstein notes, but an IAC conducted by the United States and its allies ousting the 2001 Taliban regime that resulted in change, meaning the 2001 Taliban regime must be considered an effective government despite collective non-recognition.⁹⁰

This means that the non-recognition of the Taliban by the United Nations cannot be seen as a denial of the Taliban’s existence under international law. What it is, is a punitive reaction to the Taliban’s character and political identity. This reaction, and other justifications for non-recognition, will be discussed hereafter.

3.2 Human Rights and Non-Recognition

As previously discussed in the context of governmental legitimacy, human rights obligations play a significant part of contemporary international law and international relations. It has also been noted earlier in this dissertation that states have previously, and indeed presently, refused to recognise governments of other nations as legitimate due to their human rights records. Rhodesia and apartheid South Africa’s governments were seen as illegitimate due to their racist

⁸⁷ Yoram Dinstein (n 12) 97

⁸⁸ *Aguilar-Amory and Royal Bank of Canada Claims (Great Britain v. Costa Rica)*, 1923, I RIAA 369, 381.

⁸⁹ *ibid*

⁹⁰ Yoram Dinstein (n 12) 97-98

and oppressive structure,⁹¹ and France does not recognise the North Korean government due to what it perceives as North Korea's neglect of its human rights obligations to its citizens.⁹²

Indeed, one of the few instances where universal non-recognition is recognised as a legal precedent is when the creation of a government would be in violation of a *jus cogens* international legal norm. These *jus cogens* norms include aggression, genocide, crimes against humanity, war crimes, piracy, slavery and slave-related practices, and torture.⁹³ An argument can be made that the treatment of Afghan women and girls by the Taliban regime constitutes crimes against humanity, which would void their legitimacy as a government outright. The reason I believe this argument has merit, is that when examining Article 7 of the Rome Statute, the treaty that defines what a crime against humanity can be, it defines in Article 7(h): "Persecution against any identifiable group or collectivity on political, racial, national, ethnic, cultural, religious, gender as defined in paragraph 3, or other grounds that are universally recognized as impermissible under international law, in connection with any act referred to in this paragraph or any crime within the jurisdiction of the Court...".⁹⁴ This persecution of group based on gender is entirely relevant to the Taliban's mistreatment of Afghan women and girls, and thus falls within the parameters of Article 7. It can indeed be further argued that the Taliban's extreme religious intolerance and persecution of LGBTQ citizens can also fall within the broad terms of "other grounds that are universally recognized as impermissible under international law."⁹⁵

Thus, the UN can authoritatively claim that non-recognition of the Taliban regime is based on its violation of *jus cogens* norms due to the treatment of its citizens. This is further made evident by the statements made by the UNSC with regards to recognising the Taliban in the future. On the 30th of August 2021, the Council stated that it wanted "all parties to seek an inclusive, negotiated political settlement, with the full, equal and meaningful participation of women, that responds to the desire of Afghans to sustain and build on Afghanistan's gains over the last twenty years in adherence to the rule of law, and underlines that all parties must respect their

⁹¹ JES Fawcett (n 53) 38-39; John Dugard "Convention on the Suppression and Punishment of the Crime of Apartheid, New York, 30 November 1973"

<https://legal.un.org/avl/ha/cspca/cspca.html#:~:text=The%20Apartheid%20Convention%20was%20the,declared%20apartheid%20to%20be%20criminal>. [Accessed 12 October 2022]

⁹² 'Présentation de la Corée du Nord' (n 21)

⁹³ Cherif Bassiouni "International Crimes: Jus Cogens and Obligatio Erga Omnes" (1996) 68

⁹⁴ Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, Art. 7(h)

⁹⁵ *ibid*

obligations”.⁹⁶ This may appear as prima facie evidence of the UNSC recognising the Taliban as the authority governing Afghanistan, but in my estimation it indicates terms set by the Security Council regarding the Taliban’s recognition. The UNSC has set up the condition that if the Taliban moves away from its position on curtailing women’s rights, the UNSC could consider its legitimacy. If not, the UNSC would in fact have the power to keep the Taliban illegitimate for a protracted period. This power, and the other consequences of non-recognition, will be discussed next.

3.3 The consequences of non-recognition:

Understanding why the UN does not recognise the Taliban is only part of the issue at hand. Now we must unpack what it means for the Taliban to remain unrecognised by both the UN and the major nations of the world. As noted by Dinstein, non-recognition of governments by other states does not mean the government ceases to exist, but it does have a significant impact on the “standing, rights and immunities on the internal plane – especially before the domestic courts – of the recognizing (or non-recognizing) State”.⁹⁷ If this non-recognition is then expanded to cover the entirety of the United Nations, the impact of non-recognition can be far-reaching and serious indeed.

3.3.1 The United Nations

We begin at the most fundamental area of international relations, United Nations membership. In the Afghan context, Afghanistan is a UN member state with an unrecognised government. This means that for the Taliban to be recognised as a legitimate governing body in the UN, the credentials of its delegates must be approved by the United Nations Credentials Committee as per the Rules of Procedure of the United Nations General Assembly.⁹⁸ The committee consists of nine members, three of whom (Russia, China and the US) are permanent members.

On 1 December 2021, the committee voted to defer on a motion to accept the credentials of the Taliban’s UN delegates.⁹⁹ This means that Afghanistan as a state would have its representation severely curtailed in the General Assembly, as there would be no representatives to speak in the state’s interest. Afghanistan as a state would also be left outside the international decision-

⁹⁶ “Security Council Press Statement on Afghanistan”, 16 August 2021
<https://press.un.org/en/2021/sc14604.doc.htm> [Accessed 12 October 2022]

⁹⁷ Yoram Dinstein (n 12) 98

⁹⁸ Rules of Procedure of the United Nations General Assembly, Rule 27

⁹⁹ “U.N. Seats Denied, for Now, to Afghanistan’s Taliban and Myanmar’s Junta” *New York Times* 1 December 2021

making framework, meaning it would not be able to vote on measures or resolutions that may impact its interests locally and in its immediate surroundings.

3.3.2 The International Monetary Fund

The International Monetary Fund, or IMF, is an international agency of the United Nations designed to promote international trade, stabilise global economies and to promote international economic growth. Membership of the IMF is held by 190 states across the globe. Afghanistan is a member of the IMF, but its recent non-recognition by the UN brings the efficacy of that membership into question. On the 18th of August 2021, IMF Spokesperson Gerry Rice stated that as a consequence of the “lack of clarity” surrounding the recognition of an Afghan government, Afghanistan will not be able to access its Special Drawing Rights (SDR) or other IMF resources.¹⁰⁰ This means that Afghanistan is ostensibly cut out of the international economic community, unable to ask for loans or funding from the IMF, as the IMF’s superior body, the UN, does not recognise the Taliban as the legitimate governing authority of Afghanistan.

3.3.3 The World Bank

The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development, or the World Bank, differs from the International Monetary Fund in that it was founded specifically to offer loans and development grants to low and middle-income states to foster economic growth. It is also, like the IMF, an agency founded by the United Nations. Members of the World Bank must also be members of the IMF.¹⁰¹ As these two agencies are intertwined and regulated by the United Nations, it is obvious to see why Afghanistan has trouble to gain access to the World Bank. As mentioned above, Afghanistan is locked out of the benefits of IMF membership if the government remains unrecognised. On the 1st of March 2022, the World Bank Board of Executive Directors approved expansions of the Afghanistan Reconstruction Trust Fund (ARTF). These expansions would provide \$1 billion in aid to the people of Afghanistan while notably remaining “outside the control of the interim Taliban administration”.¹⁰² This final note from the World Bank is telling of the Taliban government’s position with regards to membership. And while the World Bank notes that it is “committed to the people of

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.imf.org/en/Countries/AFG#whatsnew> [Accessed 12 October 2022]

¹⁰¹ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/about/leadership/members> [Accessed 12 October 2022]

¹⁰² <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/afghanistan/overview> [Accessed 12 October 2022]

Afghanistan,” improvement in the lives of the people of Afghanistan will be marginal at best if they have no recognised central authority to access development funding on their behalf.

Chapter 4: Conclusion:

It is evident now that the Taliban are in control of Afghanistan. The question I ask, and the question the world should resolve to answer, is how we will respond to this fact. I have noted the following regarding the Taliban’s claims to be a legitimate government and the response the international community has given them.

4.1 The Taliban as a government

Based on the criteria I have used in the above Chapters regarding the requirements for effective government in international law, the Taliban have met all of them. They are in control of the vast majority of Afghan territory. They can claim to have the obedience of the bulk of the Afghan population. They can expect to continue governing the Afghan state with some degree of permanence. They can also claim that they are independent of any outside authority or government. Thus, in a vacuum, the Taliban would indeed be the legitimate rulers of Afghanistan. The reasons for the non-recognition of the Taliban seem to be circumstantial or contextual rather than legal.

4.2 The Taliban as a terrorist organisation

The Taliban has been declared a terrorist organisation for decades. However, as I have identified above, being declared a terrorist organisation does not automatically delegitimise political authority. Where a terrorist organisation adapts to fit a state’s constitutional framework and where the organisation comes to power through constitutional means, their political authority remains legitimate.

4.3 The Taliban, political legitimacy, and human rights

Here we discussed if the Taliban’s poor human rights record as the governing authority of Afghanistan can result in an illegitimate government. I looked at the two main arguments that affirm or deny this view. The affirmation of this argument hinges on the fact that if human rights are not respected by a governing authority, they are inherently removed from the international human rights framework, as contemporary international law, and international relations view fundamental human rights as their cornerstone. The denunciation of this argument hinges on the practical implications of applying this rule fairly, and the lack of real precedent among states when it comes to declaring governments illegitimate based on their

human rights records. I concluded by stating that while human rights are central to our contemporary international legal framework, declaring governments illegitimate for human rights violations would be too cumbersome and biased a process to truly implement effectively in international law beyond the *jus cogens* norms. This means that the Taliban's human rights violations does not automatically preclude the regime from legitimacy.

4.4 The act of non-recognition:

Non-recognition, while a legal act, does not make a government illegitimate. Even where the acquisition of governmental authority was gained unconstitutionally, non-recognition does not make the incumbent regime illegitimate. There is, however, also no international law forcing a state to recognise a third-party government. The reasons why a state would not recognise a third-party government is often political in nature, but a state can refuse to recognise a government on legal grounds.

4.5 The Taliban, non-recognition, and human rights:

As discussed before regarding human rights and political legitimacy, it is my opinion that hinging recognition of a government on that government's ability to observe the human rights of its citizens is an impractical position, with little precedent in custom. However, what is supported by both international treaty and custom is the required observation of *jus cogens* norms, and that if these norms are not observed states indeed do have a right refuse to recognise a government for violating them. The Taliban have since their acquisition of political authority curtailed the rights of women and girls throughout Afghanistan. This is by itself a violation of *jus cogens* norms. This means that if the Taliban does not change or abandon its suppression of women's rights, third party states can indeed refuse to recognise the Taliban on legal in addition to political grounds.

4.6 The consequences of non-recognition:

I finally discussed what exactly the consequences of the Taliban being an unrecognised government would be. The first is that they are not qualified to represent Afghanistan at the United Nations, as the UN Security Council has indicated it is not willing to recognise them in their current state. The second is that they cannot make use of the resources provided by the International Monetary Fund, as they are not an UN-recognised government. The last is that they also cannot make use of the resources provided by the World Bank for the same reason they cannot form part of the IMF. This has led to the Taliban being locked out of the

international legal and political order and being unable to resolve the humanitarian crisis that has befallen the people of Afghanistan.

What then is the future of the Taliban as a governing authority? Speculation can only inform so far, but one can make educated conclusions based on the Taliban's current position in the international global order. The first is regarding the legality of the Taliban's governing authority. Even if, from a purely legalistic perspective, the Taliban can claim that international law gives them a substantive claim to governance in Afghanistan, the nature of their existence as former (and some would still argue current) terrorist organisation and their refusal to integrate into the human rights framework that underlies contemporary international law and international relations means that third party states will continue to deny their claims. The second is regarding the Taliban's continued non-recognition. If the Taliban wish to be seen as a legitimate government within the international community, they either must adapt and align themselves more closely with contemporary human rights standards or turn Afghanistan into a regional player of such importance as to be able to be given a "pass," a la Saudi Arabia or Pakistan.

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